

MARKETING ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TEXTILE AND CLOTHING INDUSTRY

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The textile and apparel (T&A) industry is a highly globalized, multi-trillion-dollar sector. Labor intensive, the industry has consistently relocated around the planet over the past half century in the pursuit of low-cost workers supported by preferential trade access. Today, these apparel production networks are dominated by low-cost Asian countries with very large labor-pools supplying primarily the European and United States (US) markets. The dominance of Asia in the industry has made it increasingly difficult for other producers around the world to compete, including those in Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC). Countries from LAC have participated in this globalized industry. However, there are currently no Latin countries amongst the leading ten exporters despite their proximity to the US.[8]

In recent years, advertising strategies that deeply affect the minds of customers have been developed using neuromarketing approaches. Local brands are successfully shaping the image of consumers by implementing their marketing strategies through social networks. For example, the Australian brand Sussan has updated its marketing strategy and achieved success through new campaigns aimed at young consumers. Also, the H&M brand strengthened its position in the fashion industry by presenting its premium collections at London Fashion Week 2025.[1]

Many scientific works by foreign marketing scientists have analyzed in detail the factors that form the brand concept, its impact on consumer behavior and decision-making, as well as the mechanisms for successful brand positioning in the international market. Their research considers brand management as an integral part of strategic marketing, and the scientific and methodological foundations of brand equity, image and identity in ensuring sustainable competitive advantage in the textile and fashion industries are deeply covered. In this regard, the scientific works of Keller K. L.[2], Kotler P., Mrad M., Park H., Lim R. E., Blasi S.[3], Brigato L., Sedita S. R., Mogaji E., Wei X., Jung S., Yin Z. and others are noteworthy. The research of these foreign scientists examined the practice and methodology of brand creation in enterprises, approaches to branding a trademark, scientific and theoretical interpretations of the formation and increase of brand equity, and methodological approaches to increasing brand attractiveness in the minds of customers.

From an economic point of view, the share of light industry within sectors provides the necessary raw material base and processing capacity for the development of the fashion industry. These 49 enterprises will create added value by producing clothing, knitwear and textiles for the domestic market, as well as export-oriented goods. This process, combined with the modernization of the production structure, the use of innovative technologies and the digitalization of production, will expand the competitiveness of local fashion brands in the international arena.

The dynamics observed in the country's industry during 2015–2023, especially the growth in the textile and clothing sectors, have played a decisive role in the diversification of the national economy and the creation of high value-added products. According to the table, the volume of total industrial output increased from 2.86 trillion soums in 2015 to 18.24 trillion soums in 2022, an increase of almost seven times in nine years, reflecting the strategic development of the industry, but its decrease to 4.42 trillion soums in 2023 can be explained by a short-term crisis trend under the influence of external economic factors and disruptions in the global market. In this process, the volume of textile production increased from 578.6 billion soums in 2015 to 5.1 trillion soums in 2022. soums, becoming one of the fastest growing sectors in the industry. Clothing production indicators also grew steadily, from 310.5 billion soums in 2015 to 1.72 trillion soums in 2022, which indicates that local brands are increasing their influence in the domestic market. However, the decrease in textile products to 1.15 trillion soums in 2023, and clothing production to 426 billion soums, may be due to a decrease in global demand and some logistical problems.

From a marketing point of view, the growth of the industry has become a factor that enhances the influence of local brands on the image of consumer clothing. First, the increase in production volumes has provided product diversification for different consumer segments: it has become possible to offer

cheaper and more convenient products for the mass segment, and exclusive designs and high-quality clothes for the premium segment. Secondly, by combining national traditions and modern trends in their marketing strategies, local brands were able to increase their influence on consumers' clothing image. Through the use of national patterns, environmentally friendly fabrics and local design solutions, the “Made in Uzbekistan” label became associated with national pride and quality in the minds of consumers.

The sharp decline in 2023 indicates the need to further diversify marketing strategies and ensure stability in foreign markets. In such conditions, local brands can strengthen their position through digital marketing channels, e-commerce platforms and participation in international fashion exhibitions. At the same time, pricing policy, quality assurance and communication strategies aimed at increasing the value of the national brand are of great importance to influence consumer image in the domestic market.

In conclusion, the nearly 30-fold increase in clothing production and its steady increase in the share of the industry in 2010–2022 have opened new opportunities for local fashion brands. To effectively use these opportunities, marketing strategies should be based on national design, environmentally friendly production and digital communication tools. Through this, local brands can have a strong impact on the image of consumers' clothing and strengthen their position in the international market with the “Made in Uzbekistan” label.

On September 8-10, 2024, the first joint conference of the world's two largest textile associations, the “ITMF Annual Conference & IAF World Fashion Convention 2024”, was held in Samarkand.[7]

It is important to analyze the development trends in the country's textile and garment industry and the market of local fashion brands, identify factors that affect the image of domestic consumers in clothing, and combine them with marketing strategies. As can be seen from the brand rankings presented in the table, enterprises operating in the local market are focused on different segments: large brands such as Pandora and Indenim are leaders in the clothing and accessories market, while brands such as Bellstore, Express Beauty, and Incosemantic Asia cover the cosmetics and beauty services sector. This situation indicates that the diversification of the local fashion market has created an opportunity to satisfy the diverse needs and preferences of consumers.

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